

Exploring road and points of interest (POIs) associations in OpenStreetMap, a new paradigm for OSM road class prediction

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This abstract was accepted to the OSM Science 2023 Conference after peer-review.

Completeness is the key metric in the OpenStreetMap (OSM) data quality evaluation space that assesses the number of mapped features in relation to actual objects [1]. Attribute completeness is of utmost importance for many applications. With regard to city planning, environmental risk assessment, routing, and accessibility applications, road class is important. The increasing availability of machine-derived road information, such as Microsoft Global Open Road Data, may lead to a further increase in the completeness of the road network; however, the products miss attribute information. False assumptions regarding capacity, top speed, and road quality are frequently the result of incorrect road classifications, which may necessitate routing errors in applications [2]. Therefore, an additional estimation of road class information is beneficial for many applications.

The strategic placement of Points of Interest (POIs) is not arbitrary but rather a deliberate outcome influenced by a variety of factors. Entrepreneurs and city planners serve as pivotal agents who can identify opportunities, mobilize resources, and generate value within a particular spatial and temporal context. Their deep familiarity with the historical background and specific contextual intricacies equips them with the ability to identify opportunities that might go unnoticed by others [3]. This astute awareness allows for intentional placement of POIs, creating dynamic hubs of innovation and economic activity.

In this study, we explored the answers to the question: Can we gain insights into road types by observing the locations where entrepreneurs choose to place their businesses? We looked at any connections that might exist between various road types and nearby POIs. We analyzed the co-occurrence between amenities such as gas stations, restaurants, and hotels on the one hand side and different road categories such as

Andorful, F., Lautenbach, S., Ludwig, C., Herfort, B., Fulman, R., & Zipf, A. (2023). Exploring Road and Points of Interest (POIs) Associations in OpenStreetMap, A New Paradigm for OSM Road class Prediction

In: Minghini, M., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., Liu, P., Yeboah, G., Juhász, L., Coetzee, S., Mooney, P., Sarretta, A., & Anderson, J. (Eds.). Proceedings of the OSM Science at State of the Map Europe 2023, Antwerp, Belgium, 10-12 November 2023. Available at

<https://zenodo.org/communities/osmscience-2023>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10443380](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443380)

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residential, service, and primary roads across 6 cities (Accra, Berlin, Tehran, Rio de Janeiro, Guatemala, Washington). We hope to identify stable relationships between road class and the characteristics of nearby POIs. Although roads are often considered the most complete feature in a region, road class information is frequently missing. At least in some of the cities investigated, the POIs were extensively mapped. Therefore, being able to predict road classes based on POI information seems to be an interesting option that we explore here.

To address the potential biases arising from the dominance or absence of certain road classes, we systematically assessed all road segments based on their labeled classifications. We observed that residential roads were consistently twice as prevalent as the next most common class across all the cities. However, it is noteworthy that certain classes, such as cycleways, were not uniformly distributed across all cities. For instance, cities such as Rio De Janeiro and Berlin exhibited significant cycleway networks, while Accra lacked any designated cycleways, and Washington showed a more random distribution. Additionally, road classifications, such as footways, living streets, and tracks, are relatively scarce. This limited presence may render them susceptible to overshadowing in a frequency-based analysis approach, as utilized in this study. Consequently, we made the decision to exclude road classes that had the potential to either exert undue influence or be insufficiently represented in our analysis. We focused on the six pivotal road classes outlined in the OSM Wiki (motorway, primary, secondary, tertiary, trunk, and unclassified roads).

Through visual exploration, we conducted random assessments of the POIs situated in proximity to roads within these cities. This approach has allowed us to gain a comprehensive understanding of this area. As a result of this process, we identified a set of ten distinct POI categories that collectively encompassed all observed POIs. We linked the OSM road segment with 10 POIs categories, such as amenities, shops, and public transport, based on a spatial join using a 100m (approximately two minutes) perpendicular walk distance threshold with the options of one road segment to many POIs and returned an inner join as the result. The result was a series of road segments with associated POI in the attribute. The road segment may repeat, depending on the number of POIs around it. To unravel the underlying patterns, we adopted a descriptive statistical approach, primarily cross-tabulation, to explore the raw observation frequencies between individual POIs and specific road classes. Within this framework, we estimated the mean and standard deviation for each road class in the observation matrix. The calculated z-scores then revealed the likelihood of encountering a specific road-POI pair under a normal distribution curve.

Considering that the highest probability for a singular POI to align with a particular road type was approximately 85%, we established a threshold at the 90th percentile, equating to 70% probability. This criterion serves as the basis for selecting the final candidate POIs. A hierarchical pyramid structure (see Figure 1) is designed to classify POIs based on their uniqueness in relation to specific roads. This structure comprises three distinct classes. Class 1 encapsulates unique POIs closely associated with one or two road classes. Class 2 encompasses more loosely linked candidate POIs, potentially aligning with three to four road classes. Finally, Class 3 encompassed liberal POIs distributed along five or all of the considered road classes, acknowledging the inherent uncertainty in OSM

labeling. This class pyramid provided a refined framework that was factored into labeling uncertainty.

Figure 1. Hierarchical Pyramid Used in classifying POIs based on their uniqueness.

Examining the road class and POIs associations of different cities revealed intriguing patterns in the distribution of POIs along various road types. These insights are organized within a hierarchical framework, following the pyramid structure of the methodology.

In Accra, certain POIs such as motorway junctions and gift shops align exclusively with motorway road classes. Primary roads host unique establishments, such as car dealerships, guesthouses, monuments, and wastewater plants. Secondary roads feature diverse POIs, such as chemists and furniture shops. In Berlin, motorway junctions and vending machines cluster around motorways, whereas primary roads are characterized by supermarkets. Berlin's secondary roads are marked by cafes, vending machines, and more, whereas tertiary roads feature cafes, weirs, and doctors' establishments. Taxis align exclusively with the trunk roads.

Guatemala's data lack motorway classes, which influences the distribution of POIs. Primary roads host various establishments, while secondary roads include bars, worship houses, etc.. Tertiary roads include dentists, embassies, and diverse shops. Trunk roads offer a range of POIs such as car dealerships and fire stations. Unclassified roads showcase unique elements such as artwork and bars.

In Rio de Janeiro, motorways host clinics, police stations, and towers. Primary roads stand out with railway stations, whereas secondary roads feature monuments and travel agencies. Tertiary roads host bakeries and clinics. Washington City's motorways and tertiary roads reveal a sense of uniformity with no singular POIs that distinctly define them. Primary roads encompass beauty shops, mobile phone shops, etc.. Secondary roads are unique to banks, clothing stores and supermarkets. Trunk roads display diversity from gift shops to pharmacies. Unclassified roads have POIs such as peaks and recycling centers.

During our investigation across various cities, we sought patterns within the urban landscapes. It was evident that there was no single distinctive POI exclusively associated with a particular road class across all six cities. Instead, such unique associations were found in two, three, or five of the six cities. The observed difference might be explained by the fact that the arrangement and configuration of street networks worldwide are shaped by a wide range of influences, including cultural, political, historical, technological,

design-related, climatic, and geographical factors which are beyond the scope of this paper [4]. For example, while motorway junctions were a distinct feature of motorways in Accra and Berlin, the cities of Rio de Janeiro and Tehran exhibited motorway junctions across more than two road classes, resulting in a more liberal interpretation of this POI.

In conclusion, the choice of descriptive statistics as a preliminary study over direct predictive modeling algorithms has improved understanding, as it was not only to predict road class, but also to understand how and the dynamics associated with it. Our exploration of the co-occurrence of road classes and their corresponding POIs presents promising insights into specific local contexts. This suggests the potential of predicting road types based on adjacent POIs within a given country. However, a generalized approach remains ambiguous and warrants further investigation. This study introduces a novel framework for establishing road class profiles or signatures through adjacent POIs, which can aid in predicting road class types. This approach has the potential to enrich geographic road data generated by AI models by incorporating attribute information.

The implications of these findings extend to suggest candidate POIs for road class modeling based on their geographic locations. A deeper understanding of the associations will create an established signature that can then be used to guide mappers by suggesting road classes in scenarios where POIs are mapped before the roads themselves, as we see in some places in Guatemala, thereby ensuring simultaneous quality checks as the data are updated by contributors.

Regardless, this is not free from limitations; using osm data to predict osm data is somewhat questionable because the quality is not certain. In addition, as the data continues to be updated, the association between the roads and the POIs may change; hence, this method may not be appropriate for areas where the mapping is incomplete (current work is investigating a threshold for completeness), and hence it might not work for all areas.

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